

complexes show one or two broad band(s) in the region 14 000–18 800 cm^{-1} and charge transfer band near 25 000 cm^{-1} . Cu^{II} carboxylates which are diamagnetic, show three bands¹² at 11 000, 13 500 and 26 000 cm^{-1} . Another diamagnetic Cu^{II} complex with diazoaminobenzene¹³ shows two bands at 14 900 and 18 800 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, respectively. All the Cu^{II} complexes in which the paramagnetism is partially or fully quenched absorb¹⁴ around 26 600 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the present complexes show both ligand and charge transfer bands like the spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes with diazoaminobenzene. The visible absorption spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show broad asymmetric bands at 10 600, 12 000, 15 000 and 18 000 cm^{-1} followed by a strong band at 27 000 cm^{-1} . In an octahedral approximation¹⁵ the first two bands can be assigned to the split components of ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, i.e. ${}^3B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and the next two due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) \nu_g$, i.e. ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The high frequency band corresponds to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) \nu_g$ transition. The complexes exhibit low magnetic moments¹⁶ (2.81–3.0 B.M.) which may be due to partial quenching of paramagnetism because of spin-spin interaction. The Co^{II} complexes shows bands at 16 000–20 000 cm^{-1} which are similar to the electronic spectra of known octahedral complexes^{15,17}. The spectral transitions may arise due to ligand field transition of octahedral compounds of the Co^{II} complex and may be assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition. Besides, the charge transfer band appears at 27 000 cm^{-1} . The lower magnetic moments (4.2–4.7 B.M.) of these complexes may arise either due to electron pairing for a strong covalent bond involving the 3d-electron of Co^{II} ions or spin-spin interaction.

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Interaction of Alkaline Earth Metals with Aspirin

P. N. GUPTA* and ANJU RAINA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006

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KINETIC parameters, viz. transfer coefficient (α), standard rate constant (k_a^0)_B of the overall reaction, standard potential (E^0)_B of the overall reaction and

$$k_a^* = (k_a^0)_B \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{D_{Mx}}} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{D}} \right)^{\alpha} C^{-(1-\alpha)+1} \quad (1)$$

provide evidence for quasi-reversible reduction nature of aspirin in NH_4ClO_4 at pH 4.8 in contrast with the established irreversible nature¹. The stability constant (K) of the metal ions with aspirin revealed strong complexation in the order, $\text{Ba}^{2+} < \text{Sr}^{2+} < \text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+}$. Thermodynamic functions² have been calculated to explain equilibrium condition during complexation.

Experimental

The ionic strength $\mu=0.5$ was maintained by NH_4ClO_4 . pH of the solution was adjusted at 4.8 by adding requisite amounts of HClO_4 and NH_4OH . Concentration of metal ions was kept constant at $5 \times 10^{-5} M$. Sodium alkyl sulphate, tetradecyl (C_{14}), hexadecyl (C_{16}) and octadecyl (C_{18}) (Procter and Gamble) were pure white crystalline compounds and used as such.

An universal polarograph OH-105 (Radelkis, Hungary) was used to record polarograms. DME had the capillary characteristics $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.66 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ in open circuit at $h=47 \text{ cm}$. In order to maintain precision, graphically obtained i_a and $E_{1/2}$ values were simultaneously refined by applying least-square based computer programme^{3,6}. Solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling prepurified nitrogen prior to recording C–V curves. All potentials refer to SCE. Triton X-100 (0.005%) was added to eliminate maxima and hydrolysis of aspirin. Temperatures of 25 ± 0.02 , 35 ± 0.02 and $45 \pm 0.02^\circ$ were maintained by an Ultrathermostat NBE (G.D.R.). Most of the experimental data have been obtained at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$.

Millicoulometric studies^{4,5} revealed the number of electrons (n) involved in the electrode process, with reference to standard Cd²⁺ solution.

Results and Discussion

Various workers reported⁶ the rate of hydrolysis of aspirin with magnitude of $1.0 - 21.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ depending upon temperature and media in confirmation with the well-known A_{AC} reaction mechanism⁷, depicting hydrolysis of aspirin with severing of acyl-to-oxygen bond and undergoing bimolecular reaction. The authors calculated the value of rate constant as $2.74 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at pH 4.8 from the studies of spectrophotometric analysis at 15°. The activation energy of 18–32 kcal mol⁻¹ was thus obtained from rate constants at 25° (7.9×10^{-3}) and 35° (21.9×10^{-3}). By the addition of non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 (0.005%), as well as sodium tetradecyl sulphate (0.0075%), sodium hexadecyl sulphate (0.006%) and sodium octadecyl sulphate (0.006%), aspirin indicated insignificant rate of hydrolysis. The presence of 0.005% Triton X-100 automatically was maintained throughout the study in order to check the hydrolysis. It served the dual purpose of eliminating maxima and controlling hydrolysis. At such concentration Triton X-100 (as well as sodium alkyl sulphates) showed no tendency toward aggregation (as is usually the case with associated colloids⁸) nor did it interfere with polarographic behaviour of interaction of aspirin with metal ions.

A single well-defined drawn out cathodic wave with maxima was noticed with metal ions in NH₄ClO₄. In addition to low temperature coefficient (1.5% K⁻¹), i_a vs \sqrt{h} and i_a vs C plots were linear passing through the origin, indicate diffusion-controlled reduction nature. Improved technique was tested⁹ in evaluating kinetic parameters by utilising simultaneously refined i_a and $E_{1/2}$ values. Plots of $E_{a.o.}$ vs $\log i/(i_a - i)$ were linear in all cases; slopes of which did not agree with theoretical value for two-electron transfer process, evidently due to involvement of α factor thus depicting non-reversible nature of reduction. The log plots resulted in $E'_{1/2}$ at $\log i/(i_a - i) = 0$, while the value of αn was evaluated from equation (2),

$$\alpha n = \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \frac{\Delta \log i/(i_a - i)}{\Delta(-E_{a.o})} \quad (2)$$

Invariable decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing aspirin concentration were attributed to complexation. The value of $n=2$ determined millicoulometrically introduced in equation (2) gave the α value.

For thermodynamically non-reversible reduction system^{9,10} $E'_{1/2}$ and k_o^* values have been calculated from equations (3) and (4), (25°),

$$E'_{1/2} = E_{1/11} - \frac{0.05915}{n} \left\{ \log \left\{ 10 - \exp \left(\frac{\alpha n F}{RT} (E_{1/11} - E'_{1/2}) \right) \right\} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\log k_o^* = \frac{\alpha n F}{2.303 RT} (E'_{1/2} - E'_{1/2}) - 1/2 \log t + 0.053 \quad (4)$$

and are presented in Table 1. Maximum number of ligands j in complex MX_{*j*}, prevailing in bulk of solution was obtained¹¹ from slope of plots, $E'_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_x$. The j values for aspirin complex of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ were evaluated to be ≈ 2 (Table 1). The plots being straight lines, evidently indicate single complex formation. Similarly, values of ligand number of the electroactive complex i were obtained as ≈ 1 (Table 1). Lingane method¹¹ for determining stability constant of the highest complex at $\log C_x = 0$, revealed the magnitude of $\log K$ following the order, Ba²⁺ < Sr²⁺ < Mg²⁺ < Ca²⁺. The complexes showed decrease in $\log K$ values with increase in size of the cations but owing to variations in the ionic radius, ionisation potential and polarisability, no constant pattern emerged even in a series of closely related substance. These are hardly any data available regarding monodentate complexation behaviour of ligands with alkaline earth metals which could be compared with aspirin, however, the relative weakness of complex formation by Mg²⁺ smaller than Ca²⁺ has been explained by Beveridge *et al.*¹² with tridentate ligand and with bidentate ligand¹³. Method of determining standard rate constant and potentials for electrode process is described in detail by Heyrovsky⁹. Application of the same procedure reveals that the overall reaction of complexation at the electrode is controlled by quasi-reversible nature. The calculated values (Table 1) are comparable, at least (E^0)_B, with the reported ones.

The measurement of thermodynamic functions⁹ (Table 2) was carried out at temperatures 25, 35

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF METAL IONS AT 25°

Ion	$-E'_{1/2}$ (V)	$-\log k_o^*$	j	i	$\log K$	$\log (k_o^0)_B$	$(E^0)_B$ (V)
	$C_x = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$						
Mg ²⁺	2.129	0.722.6	1.96	1.302	6.22	- 9.283	- 2.18
Ca ²⁺	2.142	0.744 1	2.02	1.06	6.59	- 2.175	- 2.14
Sr ²⁺	2.012	0.765 4	1.89	1.02	5.07	- 2.24	- 2.01
Ba ²⁺	2.022	0.686.9	1.87	1.30	4.80	- 2.24	- 2.02

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS FOR METAL-ASPIRIN SYSTEM

Temp. °C	log K	-ΔG ⁰ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-ΔH (kcal mol ⁻¹)		ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
			Calcd.	Graph.	
			Mg ²⁺		
25	6.22	8.470	—	6.71	5.89
35	6.06	8.529	6.711	6.71	5.90
45	5.91	8.588	6.714	6.71	5.90
			Ca ²⁺		
25	6.59	8.974	—	7.73	4.17
35	6.41	9.022	7.550	7.73	4.19
45	6.24	9.068	7.609	7.73	4.20
			Sr ²⁺		
25	5.07	6.905	—	5.84	3.56
35	4.93	6.939	5.872	5.84	3.55
45	4.80	6.976	5.879	5.84	3.56
			Ba ²⁺		
25	4.80	6.597	—	5.63	3.03
35	4.67	6.573	5.452	5.63	3.04
45	4.54	6.598	5.818	5.63	3.03

and 45°. The absolute values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS are nearly constant for a particular system but ΔS decreases as the ionic radius increases, thus concluding the following order of complexation, Ba²⁺ < Sr²⁺ < Mg²⁺ < Ca²⁺. During complexation the possible explanation for negative enthalpy change is due to coordinate bond formation, and positive entropy change can be attributed to disordered region in solution in the neighbourhood of central ion¹⁴. Presumably the equilibrium is

where, K is (MX)₂(H⁺)/(M²⁺)(X)².

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Spin Trapping of Carbon centered Radical formed during the Photo-oxidation of some Diols, Triols and Alditols by Uranyl Ions

ANAND G FADNIS

Chemistry Department, Holkar Science College, Indore-452 001

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THE photochemistry of uranyl ions has been extensively studied¹ and the mechanism of photo-oxidation of various organic and inorganic molecules including some alcohols has been studied in some details by the matrix isolation method² at 77K. The electron spin resonance technique of spin-trapping³ has facilitated the detection and identification of free radical intermediates formed at room temperature⁴⁻⁶. This technique makes the use of a diamagnetic spin trap, which reacts with the free radical giving rise to a relatively stable, esr observable spin adduct. The carbon (RCHOH) and oxygen (RCH₂O) centered radicals were spin-trapped during the photo-oxidation reactions of monohydric alcohols with uranyl ions^{7,8} and with other metal ions such as cerium(IV)⁹, chromium(VI)¹⁰ and vanadium(V)¹¹, platinum(IV), palladium(IV), iridium(IV) compounds¹². In this communication, the initial results of the photo-oxidation of ethane-1,2-diol, propane-1,3-diol, propane-1,2,3-triol, adonitol and mannitol by the uranyl ions are reported.

Experimental

Esr measurements were carried out on a Bruker ER 200tt instrument using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical as a calibrant. Uranyl nitrate, diols, triols, alditols and the spin-traps benzylidene-(t-butyl)amine-N-oxide (PBN), sodium-2-sulphanatophenyl-t-butyl nitron (SPBN) obtained from B.D.H. and Aldrich, were used as such.

In a typical spin-trapping experiment, a solution containing uranyl nitrate (1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³) and spin-trap (1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³) in organic substrate